

A Genetic Algorithm-Based Optimum Model for Belt Conveyor Energy Savings

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Abstract: This paper proposes to use the time-of-use electricity price as a limit and the genetic algorithm to optimize the energy consumption and electricity cost globally in order to find the optimal coal flow and operating speed in different electricity tariffs, thereby reducing the high energy consumption and electricity cost of the current belt conveyor operation mode. First, the dynamic model and energy consumption model of the belt conveyor are established, and the outcomes demonstrate that more than 30% savings in energy consumption and power cost are impossibly achieved by the optimization of transportation strategies using an intelligent evolutionary algorithm, which also has social and economic advantages.

Keywords: belt conveyor, energy savings optimization, belt model, genetic algorithm.

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Introduction

Since it has a large conveying capacity and a long conveying distance, belt conveyors are frequently used in ports and coal mines to carry commodities and objects [1]. In particular, underground belt conveyors have taken on a central role in the coal sector. As science and technology have advanced [2], researchers have been doing their own independent research and development of belt conveyors, improving their conveying capacity, conveying distance, and energy efficiency. However, the conveyor uses a lot of energy when it is actually running for a variety of reasons, which makes it difficult to realize energy savings [3]. As a result, belt conveyor energy-saving optimization has been focused. The energy efficiency of a belt conveyor is mostly determined by its speed, the way it fills with materials, how it moves, the size of the idler, and the size of the belt [4]. A conveyor is an energy converter that transforms electrical energy into mechanical energy. Four layers of energy savings are possible with belt conveyors: efficiency, operation, equipment, and technology [5]. However, when it comes to the cost and convenience of industrial sites, our attention is typically directed at the operations and equipment levels that will reduce energy consumption and prices for belt conveyors [6]. The belt conveyor's rated capacity is typically much higher than the planned production volume, so the belt conveyor is frequently in a half-load or no-load state, resulting in greater waste, and the speed of the belt conveyor remains

constant during operation, despite changes in the production plan [7]. But the above energy-saving optimization method only takes into account a single factor and doesn't take into account the time-of-use electricity price. Because the price of electricity changes at different times, there is no direct relationship between the amount of energy used and the cost of electricity. This means that there is still a lot of room for optimization when it comes to lowering electricity costs [8].

In light of the above, this work creates a mathematical model of time-of-use electricity prices [9, 10] and energy consumption in the operation of a belt conveyor. It also provides a genetic algorithm to fully optimize the belt conveyor's power use and cost of electricity. Finally, it utilizes the time-of-use electricity price as a constraint to determine the ideal belt conveyor operating speed in different time periods in an effort to lower its operational power consumption. This research suggests using the genetic algorithm to optimize the belt conveyor's ideal coal supply speed and operating speed at different times to improve its performance and efficiency, reduce production costs, and reduce energy consumption.

1. Operating a belt conveyor at a coal mine using a mathematical model

Diagram of a Belt Conveyor: When dealing with large quantities of material, a belt conveyor is the workhorse. Due to its transport capacity, minimal initial investment, and other qualities, it is frequently utilized in ports, docks, and coal mines. As shown in Figure 1, conveyor belts, idler rollers, driving rollers, and tensioning devices make up the bulk of a belt conveyor system [11]. Direct friction between the belt and the driving drum carries the coal from the coal bunker to the belt conveyor.

Figure 1 Figure 1 Diagram of a Belt Conveyor.

1.1 Run an energy-use mathematical model

It already has many different types of belt conveyors that use less energy and meet well-known standards, such as ISO 5048, DIN 22101, JISB 8805, and CEMA. Most importantly [5], these standards can't be used to reverse-optimize performance indices that have to do with how much energy a system uses. Nevertheless, in this study, we use energy use and cost as optimization metrics. Thus, a field test should be conducted to build an energy model with well-defined parameters. And then the genetic algorithm that was built gets the best possible results from its input parameters. When determining the power required to run a conveyor belt, two methods predominate. The first technique involves resistance calculation methods such as ISO 5048, DIN 22101, and CEMA standards; the second method involves energy conversion. In this essay, we use the first. In this study, we build upon the energy calculation model established in [12], simplifying and generalizing it.

Belt conveyors' operational energy consumption may be accurately predicted through modeling. Initially, the belt conveyor's force analysis is used to construct the relevant structural model, and the belt conveyor's operational data is used to identify the relevant parameters [13]. The output power of the belt conveyor drive motor may be calculated from the power consumption of the mechanical element under load [5]. The formula for the computation is as follows:

$$P_T = \frac{V^2 T}{3.6} + \theta_1 T^2 V + \theta_2 V + \theta_3 \frac{T^2}{V} + \theta_4 T \tag{1}$$

Where, $\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_3$ and θ_4 are coefficients derived from the belt conveyor's static characteristics; T is the belt conveyor's capacity to transport coal, V is the belt conveyor's operating speed.

The energy usage of the belt conveyor ' J_E' ' The formula for calculation is:

$$J_E = \int_{t_o}^{t_f} P_T(V(t), T(t)) dt \tag{2}$$

1.2 Estimating Electricity Expenses Mathematically

Currently, the energy price in Bangladesh uses the time-of-use billing model, which categorizes daily usage into three distinct phases: off-peak, standard, and peak. The daily cost of powering a belt conveyor is J_C . To do the math, use this formula:

$$J_C = \int_{t_o}^{t_f} P_T(V(t), T(t)) p(t) dt \tag{3}$$

As an example: Electricity costs $p(t)$ during various time periods. By adding the power bills for three distinct periods, the daily electricity bill J_C may be calculated. When the belt conveyor's working period is represented by the interval $[t_o, t_f]$, and its operating speed, coal supply speed, and electricity price are represented by $V(t)$, $T(t)$, and $p(t)$, respectively.

1.3 Identification of model parameter values

The belt conveyor examined in this research measures, based on data [13], 314.16 meters in length overall. Maximum belt speed is 5 m/s, with 3.5 m/s being the rated speed. Its transport capacity is rated at 1500 t/h, while its transport capacity is 2200 t/h at its maximum efficiency of 0.88. Static Parameters of a Belt Conveyor: $\theta_1 = 2.3733 \times 10^{-4}$, $\theta_2 = 8.5633 \times 10^3$, $\theta_3 = 0.0031$, $\theta_4 = 51.6804$.

The off-peak electricity price is 7.61 Tk/(kWh), the operating time is 8h, the standard section electricity price is 8.45 Tk/(kWh), the operating time is 11h, the peak electricity price is 10.56 Tk/(kWh), and the operating time is 5h. Where "tk" is the Bangladeshi currency taka.

2.0 Optimization using a Genetic Algorithm with Many Variables

In numerical calculations, iterative calculations are often used. However, traditional iterative algorithms are easy to read into the local optimum. Genetic algorithms are good at solving this problem. In order to preserve the most suited people on a worldwide scale, heredity is a way of solving problems by mimicking natural evolutionary processes, which imitate the processes of replication, hybridization, mutation, competition, and selection in the process of biological evolution. The ideal response Figure 2 depicts the fundamental process of genetic algorithm-based multivariate optimization. A suitable encoding strategy is used to transform the characteristic variables into binary-coded chromosomes after the initial circumstances and constraints of optimization have been established. The fitness function is then used to establish the limits of population evolution together with other characteristics such as the size of the population, the frequency of crossing,

the likelihood of mutation, and so on. In this method, a binary code is used to generate an initial population, and from there, an individual's fitness level can be determined. The optimal solution is then developed through evolutionary generations based on the concept of survival of the fittest, with fitness levels being the primary criterion for selecting individuals.

Figure 2 Flow chart of optimization based genetic algorithm.

To achieve the goals of energy savings, consumption reduction, and cost savings, this work uses the time-of-use electricity price as a constraint for optimization and then discovers the global optimal solution that can minimize the power consumption and electricity cost of the belt conveyor.

2.1 The determination of fitness functions and constraints

The goal of this paper's optimization is to find the global best solution that uses the least amount of energy and electricity while the belt conveyor is running. The fitness function, also known as the evaluation function in the genetic algorithm, is the key to evaluating the degree of individual superiority and disadvantage.

$$min = \frac{1}{\eta} \left(\frac{V^2 T}{3.6} + \theta_1 T^2 V + \theta_2 V + \theta_3 \frac{T^2}{V} + \theta_4 T \right) * t \quad (4)$$

The η is the efficiency of the belt conveyor, $\eta=0.8$. In this study, we configure the fitness function to maximize a given value, making it comparable to the objective function in that it aims to solve the smallest issue possible:

$$Fit(f(x)) = \begin{cases} C_{max} - f(x), & f(x) < C_{max} \\ 0, & else \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

When configuring the simulation operation, it is necessary to take into account the actual operation of the belt conveyor in the coal mine. The constraints are as follows:

- i. The transportation volume of the belt conveyor must be sufficient to meet the mine's average daily production requirements in order to maintain normal coal mine production. For a factory with an annual output of 7.2 million tons, the annual working day is 300 days and must meet:

$$Q \geq Q_{SUM}, \quad Q_{SUM} = 24000 \text{ t}$$

- ii. The upper and lower limits of the running speed V of the belt conveyor are determined by the system itself, and its range is

$$0 \leq V \leq V_{MAX}, \quad V_{MAX} = 3.15 \text{ m/s}$$

- iii. The coal supply speed T reflects the transportation capacity of the belt conveyor and is also determined by the system itself, and its range is:

$$0 \leq T \leq T_{MAX}, \quad T_{MAX} = 1500 \text{ t/h}$$

- iv. In the production process of the coal mine, it is basically guaranteed to work continuously for 24 hours, so the operating time range is:

$$0 \leq t \leq 24 \text{ h}$$

- v. The speed of the belt conveyor will change as the amount of coal being moved changes. To prevent coal spills, the conveyor's belt speed must be set to the required belt speed when the load is full, i.e., when the belt is moving the most.

$$V = \frac{T}{3.6q_m}$$

The gamultiobj function of the MATLAB optimization toolbox is used to simulate the genetic algorithm, and the following particular parameters are set, as shown in table 1.

Table 1 Parameters associated with the genetic algorithm

Parameter	Value
Population size	50
Encoding length	100
Maximum generation	100
Generation gap size	20
Crossover probability	0.8
Mutation probability	0.1

3 Analysis of simulations

The paper's optimization technique is tested by simulating a belt conveyor equipped with a multivariate genetic algorithm system in MATLAB. To aid in the optimization of coal mines for energy efficiency, the simulation results are presented in the form of a figure that shows how the electricity cost of the belt conveyor rises in direct proportion to the reduction in energy consumption.

Figure 3 (a) The Outcome of Optimisation simulation

As can be observed, the coal flow rate fluctuates significantly over time. It is important to take into account all relevant aspects, including energy consumption, electricity cost, and coal flow; however, the scheme chosen will vary depending on the factors that are prioritized.

Figure 4 The Outcome of Optimisation simulation

Figure 5 Coal supply and operating speed

The ideal solution was determined by comparing all possible outcomes with the goal of minimizing power costs; this solution had average flow rates of 1498 t/h in the peak period, 1435 t/h in the standard period, and 918 t/h in the off-peak period section. Several electricity pricing periods have varied belt speeds of 1.93 m/s, 1.87 m/s, and 1.70 m/s, respectively; all of these speeds are lower than the belt conveyor's rated speed, and the variation in belt speeds between times is minimal, guaranteeing the conveyor's reliability and safety.

Table 2 displays the belt conveyor's energy usage and electricity cost across a variety of operational modes. The first is the mode of operation currently being employed in the mine; in this mode, the belt conveyor operates at its rated speed continuously, resulting in very high energy consumption and power expenses. The second is the operating mode that doesn't account for the time-of-use electricity price but instead matches the belt speed with the output; compared to the existing operation mode, both energy consumption and electricity cost are down by more than 3% in this setting. The third operation mode is globally optimized and based on the time-of-use power price; compared to the second mode, it has slightly higher energy usage but much lower electricity costs. Hence, as compared to the other three modes of operation, improving the belt conveyor's mode of operation while taking into account the time-of-use power price might result in significant savings for coal mining businesses.

Table 2 Energy usage and electricity cost across a variety of operational modes:

Mode of operation	Energy consumption (kW/d)	Electricity bill
Current mode of operation	5947.83	50260
Time of use tariff not considered	5395.12	45589
Considered Timeshare	5128.36	43335

4 Conclusion

This paper establishes the operating energy consumption and electricity cost model for the mining belt conveyor based on its actual operation and employs the genetic algorithm to optimize the energy consumption and electricity cost dur-

ing belt conveyor operation, locating the optimal coal flow at varying electricity price points. It is of considerable importance for coal mines to save energy and reduce consumption by showing that an optimization method taking into account the time-of-use power price may significantly lower energy consumption and electricity costs under varied operating conditions.

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